

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

FIELD EMISSION OF CARBON NANOSTRUCTURES

Yurov V.

*Candidate of phys.-mat. sciences, associate professor
TSK Vostok LLP, Karaganda, Kazakhstan*

Zhangozin K.

*Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor,
TSK Vostok LLP, Astana, Kazakhstan*

Kargin D.

*Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor,
NAO "L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University",
Astana, Kazakhstan*

Abstract

Electron emission from solids, discovered in 1897 by W. Wood and theoretically substantiated in 1928 by the Fowler-Nordheim model, has become an integral attribute of modern solid-state electronics. For almost 100 years, the Fowler-Nordheim model has been supplemented many times and continues to this day (Kleshch V.I., 2024). All proposed models have one drawback: they do not take into account the size and properties of the surface layer of a solid, which is a quantum nanostructure at any temperature. In the proposed article, electron emission begins with a surface layer subjected to significant elastic stresses due to surface reconstruction. These deformations lead to the emergence of deformation energy, which, under external influence, is partially converted into heat, acoustic emission, field emission of electrons and luminescence. The essence of autoelectronic (field) emission is the emission of electrons by a solid body when exposed to an external electric field. In order for this emission to occur, the electron must overcome the potential barrier that holds the electron with the crystal field. We will consider the deformation energy as the potential barrier of a solid body. The essential difference of our model is that it allows us to theoretically calculate the threshold of autoelectronic emission of electrons from a solid body. We have shown that α -carbyne fibers should be used as an emitter instead of nanotubes. We will call the proposed model the diode model.

Keywords: emission, electron, barrier, tunneling, current, voltage, solid, carbon, diamond, graphite, graphene, carbyne.

Introduction

Modern solid-state electronics require devices with high power and small dimensions [1, 2]. For modern devices, their response time is on the order of 10 GHz and the valves on a crystal have a density of about $5 \cdot 10^7$ vent./cm² [3]. Of great importance, especially for chips, are the dimensions of parts in the nanometer range [4]. Many electronic devices and units (electron guns, lithographs, displays, X-ray cathodes, etc.) use field emission of electrons from a solid [5], which is called field or cold emission abroad [6]. Field emission of electrons from a solid is used in the manufacture of field cathodes from various materials - tungsten, molybdenum, rhenium, platinum, chromium, niobium,

hafnium and various semiconductors [5]. But the following factors interfere with the creation of a stable field cathode: sensitivity to the state of the cathode surface; ion bombardment; ponderomotive load; adsorption of gas molecules in the residue; migration of molecules on the surface, etc. [7]. To solve some of the above-mentioned problems and for microwave communication systems, IR radiation visualization, radio frequency location, etc., carbon materials began to be used [8, 9]. According to the work [7], the field emission characteristics of some structures are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Emission characteristics of the main structures [7]

Material	Emission threshold, V/ μ m	Current density, mA/cm ²	Gain factor
ZnO tapes	1,30	10,0	$1,4 \cdot 10^4$
ZnS tapes	3,55	14,6	1850
Si nanopillars	7,30	1,0	424
Nanodiamond	2,20	0,7	-
Single-walled	1,5-4,0	10,0	1000-2500
nanotubes	4,0-5,0	10-100	2000-10000
Multi-walled	0,9-20	3-10	1000-62900

In medical institutions and industrial flaw detectors, X-ray tubes with a thermal cathode are used, the

service life of which is limited to several hundred hours. A graphite cathode does not have the disadvantages listed above [8]. Graphite has a high melting point (3970 K), is resistant to ion bombardment, is chemically inactive, and has a low cost.

In Kazakhstan, Ushtogan LLP plans to mine graphite ores in an open pit from the Sarytoganbai deposit in the Aktogai district of the Karaganda region. Now the subsoil user has presented a plan for developing the deposit for 2025-2049. Research has shown that the graphite content from this deposit in concentrate can be increased to 99.998%, and, importantly, without acid cleaning.

The state-owned enterprise China Electronics Technology Group Corporation (CETC) has developed a process that allows mass production of graphite with a carbon content of more than 99.99995%. This purity is close to the theoretical limit, and impurities are reduced to almost negligible levels. The new production process of CETC allows the creation of ultra-high purity graphite.

In a recent paper [10], the models of autoemission of carbon nanostructures are described. They can be presented in Table 2.

Table 2

		Autoemission models of carbon nanostructures								
		Models		Properties of autoemission from carbon nanostructures						
Types of carbon nanostructures		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
nanotubes, conductive films	field concentration model	+	-	-	±	+	±	-	-	-
Thick films	(β-factor model)	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
Doped films	Optimum vacuum model	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Doped films	Surface levels model	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+
Loose materials	Resonance tunneling model	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-
Conductive films	Staircase model	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	+
Thin films	Two-barrier model		+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Thin films on a conductive substrate	Thermoelectric model	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

The symbols in Table 2 mean:

1. Field emission centers, which exist as small regions bordering the vacuum, in which electron emission occurs. The properties of these regions differ from the rest of the surface.

2. Emission properties are optimal if the carbon material consists of sharply defined regions – graphite-like and diamond-like, which have completely different properties.

3. Emission properties are optimal when there is an equal ratio of graphite and diamond phases.

4. Emission properties are optimal at low voltages, when the graphite-like region in the carbon material is isolated.

5. Emission properties are optimal at low values of the electron work function.

6. Emission properties are optimal when the volt-ampere characteristics obey the Fowler-Nordheim formula.

7. Emission distribution may differ from the Fowler-Nordheim formula.

8. The emission properties of carbon nanostructures are characterized by inertia and hysteresis.

9. Any emission model must contain the surface temperature.

It follows from the review [10] that the discussion of electron autoemission from solids continues to this day. In our opinion, this is due to the lack of a model of the surface layer of solids, including its size and other properties. Only after the work [11] did it become clear how to construct a model of the surface layer of solids, including electron autoemission.

The purpose of this article is to construct a model of electron autoemission from carbon materials and compare it with existing models.

Autoemission properties of solids

Here we will consider only some points on electron emission, referring readers to the works [1, 2, 8, 12-19], where a bibliography of articles on this topic is presented. For the emission of electrons from metals with an atomically smooth surface, the Fowler-Nordheim theory is used (Fig. 1), the formula of which looks like this [12-19]:

$$j \approx \frac{1,56 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot E^2}{\varphi} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{6,83 \cdot 10^7 \cdot \varphi^{3/2}}{E}\right) \quad (1)$$

Here j is the current density (A/cm²), E is the local electric field at the emitter surface (V/cm), φ is the work function (eV).

Figure 1 – Potential energy of an electron near a metal surface due to the imposition of an electric field of strength E . The total potential (solid line) is made up of the potential of the image forces and the external potential, Φ is the work function without a field, $\Delta\Phi$ is the change in the work function with a field [8].

The Fowler-Nordheim theory describes well the experimental results for metal emitters in the form of a tip, when its radius is greater than 100 nm [19]. When the emitter radius is less than 10 nm, the Fowler-Nordheim theory gives too high results [14]. The thickness

of the surface layer $R(I)$ of atomically smooth metals was determined by us in the work [20] and is shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

Surface layer thickness of pure metals (M) [20]

M	R(I), nm								
Li	2.2 (6)	Sr	5.9 (10)	Sn	2.8 (5)	Cd	3.4 (11)	Fe	1.2 (3)
Na	4.5 (11)	Ba	6.6 (13)	Pb	3.1(6)	Hg	1.8 (5)	Co	1.1 (4)
K	7.7 (15)	Al	1.6 (4)	Ce	2.8 (5)	Cr	1.2 (4)	Ni	1.1 (3)
Rb	10 (18)	Ga	2.0 (4)	Te	3.5 (8)	Mo	1.8 (5)	Ce	3.6 (7)
Cs	12 (20)	In	2.7 (8)	Cu	1.2 (3)	W	1.6 (5)	Pr	3.5 (10)
Be	0.8 (3)	Tl	2.9 (8)	Ag	1.7 (4)	Mn	1.1 (2)	Nd	3.4 (9)
Mg	2.4 (7)	Si	2.0 (4)	Au	1.7 (4)	Tc	1.4 (5)	Sm	3.4 (9)
Ca	4.4 (8)	Ge	2.4 ((4)	Zn	1.6 (6)	Re	1.5 (5)	Eu	5.0 (11)

In Table 3, atomically smooth metals are highlighted in bold according to the Jackson criterion [20]. The number of metal monolayers is given in brackets. From Table 3 it follows that the $R(I)$ layer, where electron emission occurs, has a size for most metals within 1 – 5 nm, which is less than 10 nm. For nanoscale emitters, size quantization effects begin to play a large role. Refinements of the Fowler-Nordheim theory continue to the present day [19].

Thickness and properties of the surface layer of carbon nanostructures

There are three main geometries of the carbon atom: tetrahedral, trigonal and diagonal. The tetrahedral geometry of the carbon atom (sp^3 hybridization) corresponds to the allotropic modifications of carbon: diamond and lonsdaleite [21]. The trigonal modification is formed by mixing one s - and two p -electron orbitals. The carbon atom has three equivalent $\sigma_{x,y}$ -bonds located in one plane at an angle of 120° to each other. The p_z -orbital, which is not involved in hybridization and is located perpendicular to the plane of the σ -bonds, is used to form π -bonds with other atoms. This is the geometry of carbon that is characteristic of graphite (sp^2 hybridization) [22]. Carbon with diagonal atomic

geometry forms a special allotropic modification – carbyne (sp -hybridization), however, in the materials synthesized to date, the length of straight carbyne without bends and interchain bonds is less than a hundred atoms [23]. The end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st century was marked by the discovery of fullerenes (1985) [24], carbon nanotubes (1991) [25] and graphenes (2004) [26]. Carbon nanowalls, carbon sheets, nanocrystalline graphite, etc. have acquired a special role [27]. The structural diagrams of various modifications of carbon are shown in Fig. 2.

For the thickness of the surface layer of a solid body, the following formula was obtained [11]:

$$R(I) = \alpha \cdot \frac{\nu}{S}. \tag{2}$$

Here $\nu = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is the density of the solid); $S = 1 \text{ m}^2$ is the area element; $\alpha = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ mol} = \text{const}$. The diagram of the surface layer of a solid is shown in Fig. 3a, and the dependence of ν on Z in Fig. 3b.

Experimentally, the $R(I)$ nanolayer can be measured on very pure single crystals with grazing incidence of X-rays, when the angle of incidence is equal to or less than the critical angle of total internal reflection [28].

When the angle of incidence becomes less than the critical angle, the refracted wave exponentially decays in the volume at a characteristic depth of the order of several nanometers (for example, for silicon this depth is 3.2-2.5

nm, and for gold 1.2-2.0 nm). In the R(I) nanolayer, collective-type size effects occur, and in the R(II) mesolayer, kinetic-type size effects occur [29]. There are no size effects in the bulk phase.

Figure 2. Schemes of the structure of various modifications of carbon: carbide (a); diamond (b); graphite (c); lonsdaleite (g); fullerene – C_{60} (d); fullerene – C_{70} (e); amorphous carbon (f); carbon nanotube (i), (k).

Figure 3 - Scheme of a solid: nanolayer → mesolayer → bulk phase (a); periodic change in the atomic volume of elements (b)

Using equation (2), we calculate R(I) for carbon structures (Table 4).

Table 4

Thickness of the surface layer of carbon structures [30, 31]

Carbon	T_m, K	$\rho, g/sm^3$	$R(I)_a, nm$	$R(I)_c, nm$	$\gamma_a, mJ/m^2$	$\gamma_c, mJ/m^2$
Diamond	4273	3,52	0,58 (2)	-	2991	-
Graphite	3970	2,26	0,90 (3)	2,46 (3)	2779	591
Graphene	4510	2,26	0,246 (1)	-	3157	-
α -carbyne	6081	1,90	38,6 (43)	196,7 (43)	4257	21692
β -carbyne	4757	2,00	30,2 (37)	40,0 (37)	3330	4411
Amorphous carbon	3820	1,70	1,20 (3)	3,28 (3)	2674	569

From Table 4 it is evident that for α -carbyne $R(I)_a = 38.6$ (43) and $R(I)_c = 196.7$ (128), which is significantly greater than 100 nm. It turned out that carbyne is the strongest of all known materials [23]. The specific strength of carbyne is $6.0 \cdot 10^7 - 7.5 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg, and the specific strength of diamond is $2.5 \cdot 10^7 - 6.5 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg, graphene - $4.7 \cdot 10^7 - 5.5 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg, carbon nanotubes - $4.3 \cdot 10^7 - 5.0 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg. Carbyne is the strongest material. The rigidity of carbyne is about 10^9 N m/kg, which

is twice the specific rigidity, the rigidity of graphene is $0.45 \cdot 10^9$ N m/kg. The melting point of carbyne was not measured experimentally, and was estimated by us using the method of work [32]. For graphite, the number of monolayers is 3 (Table 4), which is observed experimentally (Fig. 4) [33, 34].

We obtained the formula [11]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A(z)/A(\infty) &= 1 - R(I)/R(I) + z, & 0 \leq z \leq R(I), \\
 A(z)/A(\infty) &= 1 - R(I)/z, & R(I) \leq z \leq R(II), \\
 \dot{A}(\infty) &= \text{const},
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

where $A(z)$ is the physical property of the nano- and mesolayer with the z coordinate; $A(\infty)$ is the physical property of the bulk sample (bulk phase) (Fig. 3a).

Figure 4 - Change in graphite parameters depending on the number of its layers [33, 34].

Equation (3) shows the size effects in the R(I) layer of the exponential type, since $1 - R(I)/z \approx \exp[-R(I)/z]$.

Therefore, anomalous effects occur in the R(I) layer, for example, the classical Ohm's law is not satisfied - the

Wiedemann-Franz law is violated [35], the Ioffe [36], Rehbinder [37] effects and others occur.

The size dependence is also observed for the field emission currents of carbon heterostructures (Fig. 5) [9].

Figure 5 - Dependence of currents in heterostructures (a) and current differences (b) for forward (1) and reverse (2) connections with a potential difference between layers of 50 V on the thickness of the depleted carbon layer.

The elastic parameters of carbon structures were measured by us in [30, 38] (Table 5), where the value W_a represents the adhesion energy, σ_{is} is the internal stress

between phases γ_1 and γ_2 , and E_d is the deformation energy.

Table 5

Elastic parameters of carbon nanostructures [30, 38]

Carbon	$W_{aa}, J/m^2$	$W_{ac}, J/m^2$	σ_{isa}, MPa	σ_{isc}, MPa	E_{da}, eV	E_{dc}, eV
Diamond	3,268	-	8200	-	2,32	-
Graphite	2,853	1,690	4900	1360	2,27	1,42
Graphene	3,448	-	118400	-	2,43	-
α -carbyne	5,460	28,08	13691	68455	3,64	4,12
β -carbyne	4,290	5,72	10780	53901	3,51	3,90

The work [39] can be cited on the warping of the surface (formation of corrugations) of graphene due to internal stresses σ_{is} . It shows an AFM image of the graphene surface, from which it is evident that the surface consists of domains measuring 20 x 50 nm, oriented in

one direction and forming “folds” on the graphene surface with a height of 1 nm. In this case, the roughness value on an area of 0.5 x 0.5 μm is about $R_a = 0.25 nm$. The formation of elastic stresses at the interphase boundary σ_{is} is due to the reconstruction of the surface of carbon structures (Fig. 6) [28].

Figure 6 - Reconstruction of the surface of carbon structures

High stresses σ_{is} lead to the transformation of the surface layer of diamond, which is manifested in the

glow of graphite (Fig. 7a), and in the warping of graphene (Fig. 7b).

Figure 7 - Photoluminescence of different diamond samples [40] (a); corrugated graphene (b).

Internal stresses σ_{is} lead to the fact that in the R(I) layer all physical parameters change by 2 times (Fig. 3a) in one direction or another. For example, a 2-fold decrease in the surface energy of solids corresponds to the Rebinder effect [37]. A decrease in the electron work function is also considered to be a consequence of the size effect. We will represent a nanolayer with an area S

$= 1 \text{ m}^2$ and a size $R(I)$ of the carbon structure as a non-linear capacitor - a varicond (due to the presence of size effects) (Fig. 8a) on one of the plates of which large stresses σ_{is} develop, leading to significant deformation energy E_d (Table 5). The deformation energy first charges the capacitor, and then, under external influence (electric field, impact, friction, ultrasound, etc.), it is discharged (Fig. 8b).

Figure 8 - Varicond diagram (a); voltage change curves on the capacitor plates during its charging (1) and discharging (2) (b).

The diagram of the R(I) layer proposed by us in the form of a varicond explains the inertia and hysteresis of carbon nanostructures observed in the experiment (Fig. 9) [10].

Figure 9 – Voltage pulses (a); field emission hysteresis (b, c) [10].

We represent the nanolayer in equation (3) as a potential well, then the energy levels $E_n(z)$ in it are equal to [41]:

$$\hat{A}_n(z) = \frac{\hbar^2 \pi^2 n^2}{2m_e R(I)^2}, \quad (4)$$

If we take in equation (2) $A(z) = E_n$ - the energy level, then at $1-R(I)/R(I)+z \approx \exp[-(R(I)/R(I)+z)]$ in the

nanolayer there will be $E_n(z) = E_n/\exp[-(R(I)/R(I)+z)]$. After this, the E_n level, that is, at $z = 0$ and at $z = R(I)$ will be equal to: $E_n(z=0) = E_n/e$; $E_n[z = R(I)] = E_n/e^{0.5}$. The E_n level decreases on the graphite surface by 2.72 times, and at the boundary of the R(I) layer - by 1.65 times. All this is shown in Fig. 10a. The E_n level can be represented by Landau levels (Fig. 10b).

Figure 10 - Dependence of the energy level E_n in a nanolayer (a); quasi-discrete spectrum of electrons in a quantum well (b).

From equation (4) it follows that the energy levels E_n of the nanolayer are determined by one fundamental parameter – the constant of the metal crystal lattice a (this follows from $n = R(l)/a$) [20]:

$$E_n = \beta \cdot \frac{n^2}{l^2}, \quad (5)$$

where $\beta = \text{const}$.

The crystal lattice constant a changes in the $R(l)$ layer due to reconstruction or relaxation of the crystal surface (Fig. 6). This means that monolayers of carbon nanostructures can be represented as quantum planes with energy E_n . As soon as the parameter a stops changing, the spectrum of quantum states becomes a continuous spectrum, where the classical Drude–Lorentz laws are satisfied for nanostructures. Let us consider graphite as an example. From equation (5) and Fig. 10a it follows that the energy levels $E_n(\infty) = E_F$ is the Fermi energy

level of graphite. In [42], in the quantum-chemical approximation, $E_F = 1.5$ eV was obtained for the three-dimensional graphite model and $E_F = 2.0$ eV for the two-dimensional model. Since the $R(l)$ graphite layer is a two-dimensional medium, three quantum planes of graphite with \mathbf{a}_1 , \mathbf{a}_2 and \mathbf{a}_3 should be considered. The first graphite monolayer, graphene, has strong covalent σ -bonds C–C in the plane of the graphene sheet in combination with π -electrons outside it, which determines unique physicochemical properties [26, 43]. The motion of electrons in graphene is described by a two-component equation similar to the Dirac equation [26]. If we look for a solution to the Dirac equation in the form of a harmonic wave, we obtain the dispersion law for massless particles $E = \pm V_F k$ (Fig. 11), and the solution itself has the form:

$$\tilde{N} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \pm e^{i\theta} \end{pmatrix} \cdot e^{i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}}, \theta = \arctg(k_y / k_x). \quad (6)$$

Figure 11 - Electronic structure of graphene [26].

The Fermi surface degenerates to a point, and the Fermi energy is $E_F = 0$. This follows from a comparison of E_F for graphite and E_d from Table 5. Graphene emitters are not as popular as carbon nanotubes due to the difficulty of producing a bundle of graphene petals that

are oriented vertically. However, these difficulties are currently being overcome [8].

Bilayer graphene differs from single-layer graphene and graphite and exhibits improved physical, chemical, electronic and optical properties compared to graphene and bulk graphite materials [44]. From Fig.

10a, taking into account the work [42], it follows that E_F for bilayer graphene is $E_F = 0.9$ eV. In [45], the detection

mode of THz radiation using field-effect transistors based on bilayer graphene was demonstrated (Fig. 12).

Figure 12 - (a) Schematic diagram of a field-effect transistor based on encapsulated bilayer graphene. (b) Optical photograph of a typical graphene-based detector. The scale bar is 200 μm. (c) Conductivity of a typical DSG-based field-effect transistor as a function of gate voltage V_g , measured at 300 K, 77 K, and 10 K [45].

Three-layer graphene (Fig. 13) differs from the latter two in mobility, conductivity, and magnetic properties [46]. From Fig. 10a, taking into account the work of

[42], it follows that E_F for three-layer graphene is $E_F = 1.2$ eV.

Figure 13 - Schematic Dirac cones of three graphene layers in reciprocal space (a); enlarged image of separated Dirac cones of three graphene layers (b) [46].

Thus, we have constructed for the first time a model of the quantum structure of the graphite surface layer at normal temperature (instead of the usual low temperatures). We have shown that the Fermi energy of graphite monolayers differs sharply within the surface layer, giving different physical properties. A similar approach is valid for other carbon structures (Tables 4, 5), for metals (Table 3) and all solids without exception and even for liquids [47].

Model of field emission of electrons from carbon materials

The essence of field emission is the emission of electrons by a solid or liquid when exposed to an external electric field. In order for this emission to occur, the electron must overcome the potential barrier that holds the electron by the crystal field. We will consider the potential barrier of a solid as the energy of deformation (Table 5). The energy of deformation E_d is spent on heat, acoustic emission (propagation of sound waves), autoemission

(emission of slow electrons) and luminescence. The energy of deformation E_d is equal to:

$$E_d = W_a \cdot R(I) \cdot a = 1,5\gamma \cdot R(I) \cdot a, \quad (6)$$

where $W_a = 1.5 \gamma$ is the adhesion energy, γ is the surface energy of the solid; for most solids $\gamma = 0.7 \cdot 10^{-3} T_m$ (J), T_m is the melting temperature; $R(I)$ is the thickness of the surface layer; a is the lattice constant. According to formula (3), in the $R(I)$ layer, the physical quantity $A(z)$ decreases by half. According to reference data, the work function of electrons from graphite is $E_{ex} = 4.45 - 4.81$ eV, i.e. its average value is $E_{ex} = 4.63$ eV, and in the $R(I)$ layer $- E_{ex} = 2.31$ eV, which coincides with $E_d = 2.27$ eV (Table 5). The above means that the imposition of a field of strength E on a solid leads to the emergence of a potential equal to $P = e E R(I) = E_d$. From here we can determine the emission threshold E_{min} using Table 5.

Table 6

Emission threshold E_{min} , carbon structures					
Carbon	$E_{min a}$, V/nm	$E_{min c}$, V/nm	Carbon	$E_{min a}$, V/nm	$E_{min c}$, V/nm
Diamond	4,0	-	α -carbyne	0,09	0,02
Graphite	2,5	0,58	β -carbyne	0,12	0,10
Graphene	10,0	-	-	-	-

According to the experimental data of work [19] for graphite $E_{min} \approx 3$ eV/nm, which is close to $E_{min a} = 2.5$ V/nm. From Table 6 it follows that E_{min} is minimal for

α -carbyne. If we summarize all the features of the surface layer $R(I)$ described above, then for the autoemission of electrons from carbon structures we propose the model

shown in Fig. 14a, and its volt-ampere characteristic (VAC) – in Fig. 14b.

Figure 14 – Surface layer $R(I)$, which is a two-electrode rectifier lamp (diode) (a); VAC characteristic of the diode (b)

According to equation (3), in the nanolayer the emission current I linearly depends on $E \sim U$, and in the mesolayer the emission current $I \sim U^{3/2}$ (Langmuir formula). Further increase in the field strength leads to its saturation, and then to destruction. The mesolayer $R(II)$

$\approx 10 R(I)$ can be represented as two nonlinear capacitors connected in parallel to each other. Oscillatory processes occur in the nano- and mesolayers (Fig. 10a), experimentally observed (Fig. 15) [19].

Figure 15 - Experimental (a) and calculated map $j(\epsilon, V)$ (b), reflecting the dependence of the energy spectrum of emitted electrons $j(\epsilon)$ on the applied voltage [19].

Our model in Fig. 14a is similar to the model presented in [19]. However, our model is tied to the structure of the surface layer of a solid, and therefore is a more general theory suitable for metals, semiconductors, and carbon structures. A significant difference of our model

is that it allows theoretically calculating the threshold of field emission of electrons from a solid. From Table 6 it follows that α -carbyne fibers should be used as an emitter instead of nanotubes (Fig. 16a). We will call the proposed model in Fig. 14a the diode model.

Figure 16 - Display diagram using field emission of nanotubes (a); kinetic diagram of electron field emission (b).

The value of the emission current j is proportional to the number of electrons N , then the VAC characteristic in Fig. 14b is an S-curve, characteristic of the catastrophe theory (Fig. 16b) [48]. To describe the S-shaped curve, three objects must be considered: 1) the purpose of operation; 2) two process coordinates; 3) control parameters. In our consideration, the purpose of operation is the field emission of electrons from a solid, and the process coordinate is the emission current $j(N)$, caused by the movement of N electrons. As control parameters, we take the external field strength E and the electron work function ϕ . For one coordinate $j(N)$ and two control parameters, the catastrophe theory has only one canonical dependence for writing the dependence of the objective function [48]:

$$j(N) = 0.25N^4 - 0.5E \cdot N^2 - \phi \cdot N. \quad (7)$$

A catastrophe with such a potential function $j(N)$ is called a Whitney "assembly" type catastrophe [48]. We will analyze equation (7) in the next article.

Conclusion

The diode model of autoelectron emission of carbon structures that we proposed is also suitable for other solids and even for liquids in an external electric field. The model is based on the structure of the surface layer of solids and liquids, where the size and physical parameters of this layer are determined. It is through the surface layer that all processes with the external environment occur, including autoemission of electrons.

This scientific article was published as part of the grant funding for 2024-2026 IRN No. AP32488258. The research is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

References

1. Kirillov A.V., Kostylev A.V., Yasenev N.D. Fundamentals of Electronics. - Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation. - Ekaterinburg: Publishing house of the Ural. University, 2022. - 103 p.
2. Maksimenko Yu.N. Powerful semiconductor devices with static induction: monograph. - Novosibirsk: PVN, 2022. - 214 p.
3. Maksimenko Yu.N. Transistor with static induction KP926 with increased speed // Electronic engineering. Ser. 2. Semiconductor devices. 2022. Issue. 3 (266). - P. 51-54.
4. Bykov A.R., Zaitsev A.A., Kuznetsov D.V., Sidorov A.V. Nanoelectronics and nanomaterials. - Yelets: FGBOU VO "Yelets State University named after I.A. Bunin", 2023. - 117 p.
5. Shesterkin V.I. Emission and operational characteristics of various types of field-emission cathodes // Radio engineering and electronics, 2020, Vol. 65, No. 1. - P. 3-30.
6. Zhou Sh., Chen K., Cole M.T., Li Zh., Chen J., Li Ch. and Dai Q. Ultrafast Field-Emission Electron Sources Based on Nanomaterials // Adv. Mater., 2019, 1805845.
7. Fang X., Bando Y., Gautam U.K., Ye C., Golberg D. Inorganic semiconductor nanostructures and their field-emission applications // Journal of Materials Chemistry. - 2008. - Vol. 18. - №5. - P. 509-522.
8. Chepusov A.S. Properties of field emission cathodes made of carbon materials under technical vacuum conditions. - Dissertation of candidate of technical sciences, Ekaterinburg, 2018. - 133 p.
9. Yafarov R.K., Shabunin N.O. Contact-transport and field-emission properties of low-dimensional 2d carbon heterostructures // Microelectronics, 2023, Vol. 52, No. 1. - P. 71-76.
10. Eidelman E.D., Arkhipov A.V. Field emission from carbon nanostructures: models and experiment // Uspekhi Fizicheskikh Nauk, 2020, Vol. 190, No. 7. - P. 693-714.
11. Yurov V.M. Surface layer thickness of atomically smooth crystals // Physicochemical aspects of the study of clusters, nanostructures and nanomaterials. 2019. issue 11. - P. 389-397.
12. Gnuchev N.M. Physical processes on the surface of emission-active systems. - Dissertation of Doctor of Phys. and Mathematics. spider, St. Petersburg, 2006. - 259 p.
13. Streletsky O.A. Emission and injection properties of low-dimensional carbon materials and heterostructures based on them. - Dissertation of candidate of physical and mathematical sciences, Moscow, 2012. - 147 p.
14. Volkov E.Yu. Development of technological foundations for the production and study of the characteristics of field emission nanostructures based on graphene films on silicon carbide. - Dissertation of a candidate of technical sciences, Taganrog, 2013. - 145 p.
15. Evlashin S.A. Study of optical and field emission properties of carbon nanowalls. - Dissertations of candidate of physical and mathematical sciences. spider, Moscow, 2014. - 122 p.
16. Izraelyants K.R. Emission characteristics of carbon nanotubes in constant and weak high-frequency electric fields. - Dissertation of candidate of physical and mathematical sciences, Moscow, 2014. - 111 p.
17. Levin D.D. Development and study of the technology for forming nanostructures with a conducting channel based on grapheme layers. - Dissertation of a candidate of technical sciences, Moscow, 2015. - 139 p.
18. Zakirov I.I. Study of low-threshold field electron emission from graphene-like structures. - Dissertation of candidate of technical sciences, St. Petersburg, 2019. - 122 p.
19. Kleshch V.I. Electron emission from carbon nanostructures. - Dissertation of Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, Moscow, 2024. - 323 p.
20. Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S., Zhangozin K.N. Quantum structure of the surface layer of metals // Bulletin of the Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, 2024, No. 3 (90). - P. 93-107.
21. Belenkov E.A., Ivanovskaya V.V., Ivanovsky A.L. Nanodiamonds and related carbon materials. - Ekaterinburg: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2008. - 166 p.
22. Zhmurikov E.I., Bubnenkov I.A., Dremov V.V., Samarin S.I., Pokrovsky A.S., Kharkov D.V. Graphite in science and nuclear engineering. - Novosibirsk, 2013. - 193 p.

23. Belenkov E.A., Mavrinsky V.V. Structure of ideal carbyne crystals // *Crystallography*, 2008, Vol. 53, No. 1. - P.83-87.
24. Kroto H.W., Heath J.R., O'Brien S.C., Curl R.F., Smalley R.E. C₆₀: Buckminsterfullerene // *Nature*, 1985, Vol. 318. – P. 162-163.
25. Iijima S. Helical microtubules of graphitic carbon // *Nature*, 1991, Vol. 354(6348). – P. 56-58.
26. Novoselov K.S., Geim A.K., Morozov S.V., Jiang D., Zhang Y., Dubonos S.V., Grigorieva I.V., Firsov A.A. Electric field effect in atomically thin carbon films // *Science*, 2004, V. 306, № 5696. - P. 666-669.
27. Wu Y., Qiao P., Chong T., Shen Z. Carbon nanowalls grown by microwave plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition // *Advanced Materials*, 2002, Vol. 14, № 1. - P. 64-67.
28. Oura K., Lifshits V.G., Saranin A.A., Zotov A.V., Katayama M. Introduction to Surface Physics. - M.: Nauka. 2006. - 490 p.
29. Uvarov N.F., Boldyrev V.V. Size effects in the chemistry of heterogeneous systems // *Uspekhi Khimii*, 2001, Vol. 70 (4). - P. 307–329.
30. Yurov V., Zhangozin K. Peierls–Nabarro barrier in the surface layer of allotropic modifications of carbon // *Journal of science. Lyon*, 2024, №50. – P. 36-45.
31. Yurov V.M., Zhangozin K.N., Kargin D.B. Surface phenomena in graphite and obtaining graphene from it // *Science News of Kazakhstan*, 2024, No. 1. - P. 11-23.
32. Yurov V.M., Portnov V.S., Zhangozhin K.N., Rakhimova G.M., Rakhimova Zh.B. About the Friction Mechanism in Graphite and Diamond // *Material and Mechanical Engineering Technology*, 2024, №3. – P. 3-10.
33. Abidi I.H., Weng L.-T., Wong C.P.J., Tyagi A., Gan L., Ding Y. et. al. New Approach to Unveiling Individual Atomic Layers of 2D Materials and Their Heterostructures // *Chemistry of Materials*, 2018, Vol. 30, №5. – P. 1718-1728.
34. Yurov V.M., Zhangozin K.N., Kargin D.B. Number of graphene layers in natural graphite // *The scientific heritage*, 2024, No 143. – P. 75-80.
35. Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S. Deviations from the Wiedman-Franz law // International Conference “Scientific research of the SCO countries: synergy and integration”, Beijing, PRC. April 16, 2024. - P. 203-209.
36. Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S., Zhangozin K.N. On the Ioffe effect in the surface layer // *Endless light in science*, 2024, No. 2/2. – P. 22-25.
37. Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S., Zhangozin K.N. On the Rehbinder effect in the surface layer // *Endless light in science*, 2024, No. 2/2. – P. 26-30.
38. Yurov V., Zhangozin K. Surface layer thickness, defects and strength of graphite // *The scientific heritage*, 2023, No 128. – P. 20-27.
39. Goloudina S.I., Luchinin V.V., Pasyuta V.M. et al. Obtaining highly conductive and optically transparent films with a multigraphene structure by carbonization of Langmuir-Blodgett polyimide films // *Letters to the Journal of Technical Physics*, 2019, vol. 45, issue. 9. - P. 50-54.
40. Klepikov I.V., Vasiliev E.A. Features of the luminescence of the surface of diamond crystals // *Ural Mineralogical School*, 2022. - P. 78-80.
41. Landau L.D., Lifshitz E.M. Course of theoretical physics. Vol. III. Quantum mechanics (non-relativistic theory). - M.: FIZMATLIT, 2004. - 800 p.
42. Moliver S.S. Auger spectroscopic manifestation of electron correlation of the Fermi surface of graphite // *Physics of the Solid State*, 2004, Vol. 46(9). – P. 1537-1543.
43. Zhang T. Graphene. From Theory to Applications. – Springer, 2022. – 142 p.
44. Rozhkov A.V., Sboychakov A.O., Rakhmanov A.L., Nori F. Electronic properties of graphene-based bilayer systems // *Physics Reports*, 2016, Vol. 648. – P. 1-104.
45. Gaiduchenko I.A. Asymmetric devices based on carbon nanotubes and graphene as terahertz detectors. - Dissertation of candidate of physical and mathematical sciences. - Dolgoprudny. - 2019. - 192 p.
46. Devakul T., Ledwith P.J., Xia L.-Q., Uri A., de la Barrera S., Jarillo-Herrero P., and Fu L. Magic-angle helical trilayer graphene // *Science Advances*, 2023, Vol. 9 (36): eadi6063.
47. Yurov V.M., Zhangozin K.N. Thickness of the surface layer of water and ethanol // *Physicochemical aspects of the study of clusters, nanostructures and nanomaterials*, 2023, Issue 15. - P. 338-349.
48. Poston T., Stewart I. Catastrophe Theory and Its Applications. - Dover Publications, Incorporated, 2013. - 512 p.